

Laila 140065 Externalism

by Laila Abo El-Enein

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Abstract

Epistemology – 15POLSO2P

Externalism and Religious Belief

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Indeed, your Lord is Allah, who created the heavens and earth in six days and then established Himself above the Throne. He covers the night with the day, [another night] chasing it rapidly; and [He created] the sun, the moon, and the stars, subjected by His command. Unquestionably, His is the creation and the command; blessed is Allah, Lord of the worlds. (Quran, 7:54)

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Introduction

Internalism, mainly defined as a person's ability to justify a belief based only on internal affairs (Poston), seems perhaps the best method to reach a dogmatic religious belief. However, externalists can also reach a dogmatic religious belief, whilst depending on factors that aren't restricted to a person's internal thoughts but rather external factors around them. Regardless of how the Gettier cases may seem to disapprove of adequate justifications to be equivalent to knowledge (Gettier, 1963), it can also be utilized to validate dogmatic religious beliefs. One's internal logic to justify his beliefs may be experiences one has been through or memories that have strained his thoughts to believe that an external higher power is responsible for creation and one's believing in the term destiny. Therefore, it is only logical for an internalist to easily believe in God. For externalists, their ideology that demands a physical external proof (Poston) makes it quite difficult for dogmatic religious belief to be instilled in them. However, this is what this paper will attempt. This paper aims to argue that certain factors can be viewed in an externalist method to prove God's existence. Thus, this paper will first define internalism, the second section will elaborate on externalism, and the third section will then attempt to use externalist approaches to obtaining knowledge to justify the true belief of religion. The paper will then conclude by summarizing all the afore-mentioned points and relating them once more to the paper's argument.

Internalism

As its name would suggest, internalism relies on the notion of being internal. For an internalist to dub something as knowledge, it depends on one's internal factors, such as their mental state or "reflectively-accessible" state. This accessibilism notes in its meaning that only through reflection can a person decide between two contradictory beliefs. Des Cartes believed that if a person can determine the relation between their beliefs and experiences, that relation will be reflectively accessible, however, academics refute this. Propositional justification and "the causal origins of one's belief" are not attainable as easily, if at all, as Des Cartes claims (Poston). Should this be related to religious belief, it is sufficient to say that most religious fundamentalists use terminology that is internalist, such as self-evident and non-questionable. Accordingly, for internalists to have basic beliefs, their rationality and reason is determined by the "mental inspection of one's own beliefs (Clark)." Hence, it can easily be determined that internalists are likely to embrace a dogmatic religious belief as said belief will depend on their inner thoughts and experiences, reasoning with the circumstances around them without the influence of skepticism. It can be said that religious internalists can feel the divinity of the Creator within their own selves.

Externalism

Dutifully, externalism must be defined as well, in order to do so, a slight comparison is inevitable:

Internalists maintained that knowledge requires justification and that the nature of this justification is

completely determined by a subject's internal states or reasons. Externalists denied at least one of these commitments: either knowledge does not require justification or the nature of justification is not completely determined by internal factors alone. (Poston)

Therefore, an externalist JTB (justified true belief) is dependent on several options: whether it is based on a consistent "belief-producing" progression, whether it is counterfactually reliant on a state of affairs or it is caused by said set of circumstances (Poston). None of which identify as internal factors, therefore, externalism is dependent on majorly-materialistic factors, mostly, that are external although not completely foreign to one's internal factors (Alweiss, 2009). Although substantial evidence is not uncommon, many externalists would deny the existence of a divine entity as they do not "see" God. However, with considerable, extensive and significant research, using an externalist approach to knowledge, the belief-producing process and the reliance on knowledge being caused by a state of affairs, examining Holy texts brings about non-internal justifications to the ultimate question of God's existence.

Examining the Holy Quran

In the era of doubt in dogmatic religious beliefs due to claimed lack of evidence, it is indispensable to examine holy texts and extract physical scientific

evidence that disprove atheist theories. In this paper's attempt at using externalist approaches to prove that God exists, following will commence an interpretation of certain verses in the Quran that are extremely relevant to human development.

"And it is We who have constructed the heaven with might, and verily, it is We who are steadily expanding it." (The Qur'an, 51:47). The term heaven does not only refer to gardens of the afterlife, but also of the universe. In the 20th century, American astronomer Edwin Hubble was observing the stars when he noticed that they were constantly moving away from each other. With further technology and scientific research, it was proven that since the distance was increasing, it also meant that the universe was expanding (Gross, 2016), which was explained in the ayah above.

Another ayah that proves Quran had illustrated astronomy at least centuries before modern telescopes were invented is the following "It is He Who created the night and the day, and the sun and the moon. They swim along, each in an orbit." (The Qur'an, 21:33) and "By the sky full of paths and orbits."(The Qur'an, 51:7). In these verses, the concept of orbits is explained. Although at the time of Prophet Muhammad it would have been almost impossible to physically prove this, modern science and technology explained the revolving and rotating motions of the planets and other celestial objects (Jordan, 2016).

Further proof would be of how which the Quran explained the atmosphere, and the earth's habitability due to its air components that aren't obtainable on other planets. "We made the sky a preserved and protected roof yet still they turn away from Our Signs..."(The Qur'an, 21:32). The earth is surrounded by its atmosphere,

which comprises a number of gases, predominantly nitrogen and oxygen. They are in the most adequate numbers and ratios suitable for sustaining human life, and should a person rise further than the designated atmosphere, they will need special breathing equipment (North Carolina State University, 2013). Hence, the Quran has already mentioned this scientific fact and proves human need of this atmosphere, a form of protection, so it would maintain water and human life.

Therefore, with proof from the texts of the Holy Quran, the book dictated to his Prophet Muhammad through the angel Gabriel, stating scientific facts that were later discovered through technology more than centuries before the discoveries actually took place is perhaps the most adequate proof to a justified true belief in the existence of God, the higher power that has created the universe.

Conclusion

Ultimately, although internalists are more likely to have dogmatic religious belief due to the nature of their approach to justifying knowledge, which is reliant on one's internal affairs and mind and bodily states, externalists can also use their external approach to justifying true belief in establishing a religious faith and endorsing in it. This is done through examining religious texts, such as the Quran, and noting how there are verses that predict the scientific discoveries that will be made in later centuries, such as the realisation of the earth's atmosphere, the cosmos and the expansion of the universe. With that structure, this paper has reached its argument that externalist approaches to knowledge can prove that God exists.

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